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Scale/Size Dependency of Intact Rock under Point Load and Indirect Tensile (Brazilian) Testing

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Abstract:	<p>The problem of scale-size dependency of intact rock has been extensively investigated with a particular focus on uniaxial compressive strength while a limited number of studies have included point load and tensile testing. Despite advancement in such experimental researches, analytical investigation has not attracted the same amount of attention. In this paper, the scale-size dependency of intact rock under point load and indirect tensile testing conditions has been studied experimentally and analytically using different rock types with various geological origins including sedimentary, igneous and metamorphic. From the comparison of the experimental results, it was concluded that all rock types follow the generalized size effect concept where strength reduces with an increase in size. Also, it was confirmed that under indirect tensile testing with an increase in size, the failure of rock transfers from pure tension to a combination of shearing and tension. In addition, the applicability of different size effect models (statistics, fracture energy and multifractals) to experimental data was assessed. It was thus concluded that the models with two constants fit the point load strength data more accurately. The size effect model based on fracture energy theory provided the best fit to the tensile strength data whereas the statistical size effect model provided the least best fit.</p>
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<p>If yes, please provide justification in the comments box below.</p> <p>as follow-up to "Authors are expected to present their papers within the page limitations described in Publishing in ASCE Journals: A Guide for Authors. Technical papers and Case Studies must not exceed 30 double-spaced manuscript pages, including all figures and tables. Technical notes must not exceed 7 double-spaced manuscript pages. Papers that exceed the limits must be justified. Grossly over-length papers may be returned without</p>	<p>Due to large number of references and figures this limitation has exceeded otherwise the MS has about 3800 words excluding references which is the reasonable number for technical papers. All the figures to be in high quality have been provided at very large size so that would be easy for reviewing process. Please note that I have already published two papers in this journal in the same length as this submission. The first paper titled "Unified Size Effect Law for Intact Rock" was in fact longer than this MS. Thus it should fit within the expectation of IJG.</p>

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27 February 2017

Professor Musharraf Zaman
Honorary Editor in Chief
International Journal of Geomechanics
zaman@ou.edu

Dear Musharraf,

NEW MANUSCRIPT SUBMISSION

I am pleased to submit electronically a copy of a manuscript to be considered for possible publication in the International Journal of Geomechanics.

The manuscript is titled 'Scale/size dependency of intact rock under point load and indirect tensile (Brazilian) testing'. This is an original manuscript which has not been submitted for publication anywhere else.

Possible reviewers for you to consider include:

Professor Shinichi Akutagawa, Kobe University, cadax@kobe-u.ac.jp

Professor Dwayne Tennant, The University of British Columbia, dwayne.tennant@ubc.ca

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Associate Professor Masahiko Osada, Geosphere Research Institute of Saitama University, Osada@saitama-u.ac.jp

Each is active in novel practical and analytical aspects of rock mechanics.

I look forward to hearing from you with the reviewer comments.

Sincerely

Hossein Masoumi
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Scale/Size Dependency of Intact Rock under Point Load and Indirect Tensile (Brazilian) Testing

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Abstract

The problem of scale-size dependency of intact rock has been extensively investigated with a particular focus on uniaxial compressive strength while a limited number of studies have included point load and tensile testing. Despite advancement in such experimental researches, analytical investigation has not attracted the same amount of attention. In this paper, the scale-size dependency of intact rock under point load and indirect tensile testing conditions has been studied experimentally and analytically using different rock types with various geological origins including sedimentary, igneous and metamorphic. From the comparison of the experimental results, it was concluded that all rock types follow the generalized size effect concept where strength reduces with an increase in size. Also, it was confirmed that under indirect tensile testing with an increase in size, the failure of rock transfers from pure tension to a combination of shearing and tension. In addition, the applicability of different size effect models (statistics, fracture energy and multifractals) to experimental data was assessed. It was thus concluded that the models with two constants fit the point load strength data more accurately. The size effect model based on fracture energy theory provided the best fit to the tensile strength data whereas the statistical size effect model provided the least best fit.

Keywords: point load strength index; tensile strength; statistical model; size effect law; multifractal scaling law

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28 **Introduction**

29 Scale-size dependency of intact rock has been the central focus of various studies over the
30 last four decades. Both terms (scale and size) have been used to refer to the influence of three
31 dimensional volumetric changes on the mechanical characteristics of intact rock.

32

33 A large portion of size effect studies on intact rock have been conducted under uniaxial and
34 triaxial compression (Mogi 1962; Lundborg 1967; Bieniawski 1968; Pratt et al. 1972; Singh
35 and Huck 1972; Dhir and Sangha 1973; Hunt 1973; Bieniawski 1975; Abou-Sayed and
36 Brechtel 1976; Baecher and Einstein 1981; Panek and Fannon 1992; da Silva and Hennies
37 1993; Kramadibrata and Jones 1993; Hawkins 1998; Aubertin et al. 2000; Thuro et al. 2001a;
38 Yoshinaka et al. 2008; Darlington et al. 2011; Masoumi et al. 2012; Masoumi et al. 2014;
39 Masoumi et al. 2016a; Masoumi et al. 2016b; Roshan et al. 2016a) some have considered
40 point loading (Broch and Franklin 1972; Bieniawski 1975; Brook 1977; Wijk 1978; Brook
41 1980; Greminger 1982; Brook 1985; Hawkins 1998; Thuro et al. 2001b; Masoumi et al.
42 2012; Forbes et al. 2015) and only few have considered tensile testing (Wijk 1978; Andreev
43 1991a; Andreev 1991b; Butenuth 1997; Thuro et al. 2001a; Çanakcia and Pala 2007). Due to
44 the complexity of the direct tensile testing, the indirect tensile testing known as Brazilian test
45 is a common alternative.

46

47 Most of the studies on size dependency of intact rock have attempted to address this problem
48 from an experimental viewpoint while the need for analytical models is essential for practical
49 applications. In general, for brittle and quasi brittle materials such as rock and concrete, three
50 major size effect models have been proposed based on statistics (Weibull 1939), fracture
51 energy (Bazant 1984) and multifractals (Carpinteri et al. 1995). All these models indicate that

52 with an increase in size the strength decreases. Darlington et al. (2011) assessed the
53 applicability of these models to a set of uniaxial compressive strength (UCS) data from
54 different geological origins to identify the one that fits each set of rock types the best.
55 However, there is no similar study to that of Darlington et al. (2011) for point load and tensile
56 strength data.

57

58 The determination of UCS is an often used parameter in most rock mechanics projects while
59 rock failure in tension is also important in practice (Hoek and Brown 1980; Goodman 1989;
60 Brady and Brown 2006). In both tensile and point load testing, the intact rock fails in tension
61 as demonstrated by Russell and Muir Wood (2009) and Masoumi et al. (2016c). Hence,
62 consideration was given to both of these testing regimes in assessing the problem of size
63 dependency of intact rock under tension.

64

65 A comprehensive set of laboratory experiments consisting of point loading and Brazilian tests
66 were conducted on different rock types from various geological origins including
67 sedimentary, igneous and metamorphic. The experiments were conducted according to the
68 relevant ISRM (2007) suggested methods. Finally, the applicability of different size effect
69 models to point load and tensile strength data was assessed similar to that carried out by
70 Darlington et al. (2011) for UCS data.

71

72 **Rock Types**

73 Six different rock types were selected for experimental investigation. Gosford sandstone was
74 studied using point load and indirect tensile (Brazilian) tests. Other rock types, namely,

75 Bentheim sandstone, Gambier limestone, granite and marble were also examined but using
76 point loading only.

77

78 Bentheim sandstone was sourced from Gildehausen quarry, near the village of Bentheim in
79 Germany. The rock type is similar to the reservoir rock from Schoonebeek oil field with
80 approximately 23% porosity. It is relatively homogenous (see Fig. 1a) with approximately
81 95% quartz, 3% kaolinite and 2% orthoclase. The quartz grain size varies between 0.05 and
82 0.5 mm (Klein et al. 2001; Baud et al. 2004).

83

84 Gambier limestone (see Fig. 1b) was extracted from the Mount Gambier coastal region in
85 South Australia. The rock is the product of shoreline sedimentation during successive
86 interglacial maxima and various interstadials (Murray-Wallace et al. 1999). A couple of
87 studies have investigated the geological and micro structure of this limestone (Allison and
88 Hughes 1978; Melean et al. 2009). Melean et al. (2009) reported the porosity of this rock to
89 be approximately 50%.

90

91 Gosford sandstone was obtained from Gosford Quarry, Somersby, New South Wales,
92 Australia (see Fig. 1c). Samples were carefully selected to be as homogeneous as possible.
93 The maximum grain size of this sandstone was reported by Masoumi et al. (2016d) to be 0.6
94 mm. The detailed microstructural information and petrography of Gosford sandstone have
95 been reported by Roshan et al. (2016b) and Masoumi et al. (2016d), respectively. It is
96 noteworthy that only Brazilian tests were conducted on Gosford sandstone in this study and
97 the point load strength indices reported by Masoumi et al. (2016d) were included for
98 analytical size effect investigation.

99 The crystal size was used to differentiate between two granite types (see Figs. 1d and 1e).
100 The granite with larger crystals (ranged between 3 and 5 mm) was labelled A while the small
101 crystal sized sample ranging between 1 and 2 mm was labelled Granite B. Both granites
102 consist of quartz, plagioclase feldspar, biotite mica and finely disseminated iron oxides
103 (Savidis 1982). The average bulk densities of the Granites A and B were estimated to be 2766
104 and 2588 kg/m³, respectively.

105

106 The marble samples used in this study came from Wombeyan, New South Wales, Australia
107 (see Fig. 1f). Based on the Savidis (1982) study, this marble mostly consists of calcite and its
108 average bulk density was estimated to be 2758 kg/m³.

109

110 **Experimental Procedure**

111 The samples were prepared in accordance with the ISRM (2007) suggested methods and
112 tested in a completely dry condition (oven dried for 24 hours at 105°C temperature).

113

114 ***Point Load Testing***

115 All the point load tests (PLT) were conducted under axial loading condition according to
116 ISRM (Franklin 1985) suggested method where the ratio of length over diameter can vary
117 from 0.3 to 1 ($0.3 \leq L/D \leq 1$). In the axial point loading the force is applied at the centre of the
118 end surfaces and the point load strength index (I_s) is estimated using the following equation:

$$119 \quad I_s = \frac{P}{4A/\pi} \quad (1)$$

120 where A is the minimum cross sectional area of a plane through the platen contact points and
121 P represents the axial force.

122 For Bentheim sandstone and Gambier limestone the sample sizes ranged from 19 mm to 65
123 mm diameters and more experiments were conducted on small diameters (Tables 1 and 2).
124 Considering the standard deviations (SD) and coefficient of variations (CV) at different sizes,
125 it is evident that the scatter of the Bentheim sandstone data is significantly less than that of
126 the Gambier limestone. However, it should be noted that the measured I_s values from the
127 Gambier limestone were approximately half of that of the Bentheim sandstone. Higher
128 homogeneity in the Bentheim sandstone potentially caused less scatter in the data. Figs. 2 and
129 3 present the size effect trends of Bentheim sandstone and Gambier limestone, respectively
130 which show the decrease in strength with an increase in size. Figs. 4 and 5 illustrate the
131 typical fracture patterns from the axial point load tests on Bentheim sandstone and Gambier
132 limestone, respectively. A single fracture that led to two broken pieces was the most
133 dominant failure pattern in the point load tests conducted on Bentheim sandstone and
134 Gambier limestone at different sizes.

135

136 The sample diameters of Granite A varied between 19 and 50 mm diameters. For Granite B
137 diameters ranged from 18 mm to 96 mm. Tables 3 and 4 list the average point load strength
138 indices, the number of tests at different sizes, SD and CV obtained from the point load testing
139 on these two granite samples. The resulting CVs from both granites were approximately less
140 than 22% for almost all sizes. Figs. 6 and 7 show the graph of point load indices versus
141 sample diameter which follows the generalised size effect concept where strength decreases
142 with an increase in size. Also, the typical fracture patterns from the axial PLT on Granites A
143 and B are presented in Figs. 8 and 9.

144

145

146 Marble was the only metamorphic rock which was tested here under axial point loading. The
147 sample sizes for this rock varied from 19 mm to 96 mm diameter and Table 5 lists the
148 resulting experimental data from the point load tests. From Table 5 it is evident that the CVs
149 are greater than 20% for 19, 50 and 65 mm diameters. It is believed that this is associated
150 with the existence of a weathered plane (defect) randomly spreading across the marble block
151 before the coring process. Identification of such a weak plane was very difficult through only
152 observation but attempts were made to avoid any coring from the affected zones. It could still
153 however affect the results at microscale. The point load strength indices obtained from
154 marble (see Fig. 10) samples are in agreement with the basic size effect theory (Weibull
155 1951). There were however two diameters (38 and 96 mm) where the mean strength indices
156 placed slightly below and slightly above the expected trend. Fig. 11 illustrates the typical
157 fracture patterns of marble samples tested under axial point loading. Single fracture was the
158 common failure pattern in this rock.

159

160 ***Indirect Tensile (Brazilian) Testing***

161 For Brazilian test, ISRM (Bieniawski and Hawkes 1978; ISRM 2007) proposed length to
162 diameter ratios between 0.3 and 0.6, thus 0.5 has been selected as an appropriate ratio in this
163 study. A total of 40 tests were conducted on Gosford sandstone according to ISRM (2007)
164 suggested method. The sample sizes ranged from 19 mm to 145 mm diameters. The tensile
165 strength is calculated using the following formula (Bieniawski and Hawkes 1978; ISRM
166 2007):

$$167 \quad \sigma_t = \frac{2P}{\pi Dt} \quad (2)$$

168 where P is the peak load at failure, D is the diameter and t is the thickness of the sample
169 measured at the center.

170 The mean tensile strengths for Gosford sandstone samples as well as the number of
171 repetitions for each size are given in Table 6. The overall scatter for Brazilian results is less
172 than 15% in all sizes, except for the 25 mm diameter which resulted in about 24% coefficient
173 of variation. Fig. 12 shows the variation of the tensile strength data versus sample diameter
174 for Gosford sandstone. In general, a descending trend is observable from the tensile strength
175 data ranging from 19 mm to 118 mm diameters where the increase in size leads to decrease in
176 strength. By contrast, the resulting tensile strength data for 145 mm diameter samples does
177 not follow this trend and lies significantly above the mean strengths of almost all other sizes.
178 This is an interesting observation which is reported here for the first time and it is believed to
179 be associated with the fracture pattern of 145 mm diameter samples under Brazilian test.

180

181 According to ISRM (2007) suggested method only single axial fracture at the center of the
182 sample is a valid failure pattern for Brazilian test. Fig. 13 highlights the difference between
183 the failure patterns resulted from 145 mm diameter samples and those obtained from other
184 sizes. Fig. 13 shows that for the largest samples, an axial fracture at the centre along with the
185 extra shearing zones developed at the contact points between the samples and the
186 compressive loading frame. This behaviour was studied by Sertai et al. (2015) through an
187 extensive analytical investigation who argued that the concentration of shear stresses
188 developed in the vicinity of contacts can interfere with the tensile breakage of disc samples
189 through the formation of inverse shear conical plugs and multiple cracking. It has been
190 reported by different researchers (Erarslan and Williams 2012; Serati 2014; Komurlu and
191 Kesimal 2015; Serati et al. 2015) that in hard and brittle materials it is impractical to follow
192 the standard Brazilian test methodology in its entirety (see Fig. 14). Deviations from the
193 standard test method arise mainly from the violation of the accepted boundary conditions in a
194 conventional Brazilian test. The flexural tensile strength measured at the centre of a solid

195 Brazilian disc, therefore, could easily lead to erroneous estimations of the actual tensile
196 strength of the material if the test method employed deviates significantly from the standard
197 test method. Thus, it can be hypothesised that by increase in sample size the stored energy
198 inside the Gosford sandstone sample becomes higher and therefore the behaviour of rock
199 becomes similar to hard rock materials leading to inaccurate measurement of tensile strength.
200 As a result, the tensile strength data from 145 mm diameter samples were excluded for size
201 effect modelling process.

202

203 **Comparative Study**

204 In this section the experimental results obtained from different sizes are compared with well-
205 known size effect models based on statistics, fracture energy and multifractals to investigate
206 the applicability of them to point load and tensile strength data and identified the one that has
207 the best fit to the experimental data. Masoumi et al. (2016d) has extensively reviewed these
208 models and elaborated their features through comprehensive discussion as well as some
209 graphical representations. Below is a brief summary from Masoumi et al. (2016d) study on
210 these models.

211

212 *Size Effect Models*

213 Statistical Model

214 The statistical theory was initially proposed by Weibull (1939) followed by an improvement
215 to the original concept by Weibull (1951). The theory is commonly known as the weakest
216 link theory and states that the probability of failure under any load can be attributed to
217 structural flaws inherent in solids. If the probability of an element to survive under load is
218 assumed $1 - P$ where P is the probability of the element to fail, then the survivability of the

219 entire chain of n elements is the accumulative probability which equals to $(1-P)^n$ or $1-P_f$
220 where P_f is the probability of failure of the chain and therefore:

$$221 \quad 1 - P_f = (1 - P)^n \quad (3)$$

222 then:

$$223 \quad \ln(1 - P_f) = n \ln(1 - P) \quad (4)$$

224 In practice P is very small and thus $\ln(1 - P) \approx -P$. Hence:

$$225 \quad \ln(1 - P_f) = -nP \quad (5)$$

226 The number of elements, n in a chain situation can be replaced by the representative volume
227 of the material, V/V_r , as shown below:

$$228 \quad \ln(1 - P_f) = -(V/V_r)P \text{ or } P_f = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{V}{V_r}P\right] \quad (6)$$

229

230 A general form of Eq. (6) was proposed by Weibull (1939) and then an additional variable, m
231 was added for better model simulation (Weibull 1951) according to:

$$232 \quad m \log\left(\frac{P_f(\sigma)}{P(\sigma)}\right) = \log\left(\frac{V}{V_r}\right) \quad (7)$$

233

234 In Eq. (7) V and V_r can be substituted by any characteristic measure of size such as length or
235 sample diameter. A modified formulation of statistical model (Eq. 7) was proposed by Brook
236 (1980; 1985) to predict the size effect in point load tests as follows:

$$237 \quad \frac{I_s}{I_{s50}} = \left(\frac{50}{d} \right)^{k_1} \quad (8)$$

238 where, I_s is the point load strength index, I_{s50} is the characteristic point load strength index
 239 obtained from a sample with the characteristic size of 50 mm, d is sample size and k_1 is a
 240 positive constant controlling the statistical decay of the strength with raise in size which is
 241 also related to m in Eq. (7).

242

243 Fracture Energy Model

244 A size effect model based on the fracture energy theory was proposed by Bazant (1984) who
 245 postulated that a zone of microcracking that precedes the fracture energy would occur in most
 246 brittle and quasi-brittle materials such as rock and concrete. Bazant (1984) then quantified the
 247 fracture energy and incorporated this energy into the formulation of size effect law (SEL)
 248 according to:

$$249 \quad \sigma_N = \frac{Bf_t}{\sqrt{1 + (d / \lambda d_0)}} \quad (9)$$

250 where σ_N is a nominal strength, B and λ are dimensionless material constants, f_t is a strength
 251 for a sample with very small size, d is the sample size and d_0 is the maximum aggregate size.

252

253 Multifractal Model

254 Fractals have been implemented to study different properties in rocks. Carpinteri (1994) and
 255 Carpinteri and Ferro (1994) argued that the self-similar properties of multiple cracks can
 256 appear in a wide range of material sizes and therefore making them fractal. Carpinteri et al.

257 (1995) proposed the multifractal scaling law (MFSL) based on the topological concept of
258 geometrical multifractality with the following analytical expression:

$$259 \quad \sigma_N = f_c \sqrt{1 + \frac{l}{d}} \quad (10)$$

260 where σ_N is the nominal strength, l is a material constant with unit of length, f_c is the strength
261 of a sample with an infinite size which may be expressed in terms of an intrinsic strength, and
262 d is the sample size. In general, statistical model, SEL and MFSL act similar to each other in
263 which the strength decreases as size increases.

264

265 *Applicability of Existing Size Effect Models to Point Load Results*

266 Here, the applicability of the three main size effect models (statistical, SEL and MFSL) to the
267 point load results obtained from sedimentary, igneous and metamorphic rocks is examined
268 using an analytical approach.

269

270 The point load results for Gosford sandstone reported by Masoumi et al. (2016d) under axial
271 loading were also included here for extensive analytical study. It is aimed to identify which
272 size effect model provides the best fit to the experimental data based on the coefficient of
273 multiple determination (R^2) values.

274

275 For sedimentary rocks, the resulting size effect comparative analysis is presented in Table 7.
276 Also, Figs. 15a, 16a and 17a illustrate the comparison between the model predictions and the
277 experimental data. To further assess the deviation of the model predictions from each data
278 point, the relative error (RE) for each rock types at tested diameters were also calculated

279 according to Roshan et al. (2012) study and the results are shown in Figs. 15b, 16b and 17b
 280 for Bentheim sandstone, Gambier limestone and Gosford sandstone, respectively. As can be
 281 seen from Figs. 15 to 17 and Table 7, the SEL and MFSL generally show a more accurate fit
 282 to the data compared to statistical model. It is believed that the presence of two fitting
 283 parameters in SEL and MFSL give more flexibility to the mathematical form to fit better to
 284 the experimental data.

285

286 The applicability of existing size effect models to the point load results from Granites and
 287 Marble samples were investigated. As these rocks have a crystalline structure they were
 288 grouped together. The resulting fitting constants are listed in Table 8 followed by graphical
 289 representations and RE comparisons in Figs. 18 to 20. In Fig. 19 almost all three models'
 290 predictions are alike whereas in Figs. 18 and 20, SEL and MFSL better fit the data compared
 291 to statistical model.

292

293 Finally, the normalised mean axial point load strength indices for all rock samples grouped
 294 together for the best fits of statistical model, SEL and MFSL as shown in Fig. 21. All the
 295 axial point load strength indices were nondimensionalised using the average 50 mm diameter
 296 point load strength index. As a result, some modifications were required in SEL and MFSL,
 297 respectively according to:

$$298 \quad \frac{\sigma_N}{\sigma_{N50}} = \frac{\sqrt{1 + (50/\lambda d_0)}}{\sqrt{1 + (d/\lambda d_0)}} \quad (11)$$

$$299 \quad \frac{\sigma_N}{\sigma_{N50}} = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{l}{d}}}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{l}{50}}} \quad (12)$$

300 Table 9 lists the fitting constants for statistical model, modified SEL (Eq. 11) and modified
 301 MFSL (Eq. 12). It is evident from Table 9 that the resulting R^2 from statistical model and
 302 modified SEL and MFSL are the same when all rock samples were grouped together. This
 303 could be associated with the modification process applied to SEL and MFSL (Eqs. 11 and 12)
 304 where one of the constants during the normalisation process was eliminated. Also, it is
 305 evident that the resulting k_1 for statistical model is approximately the same as that suggested
 306 by ISRM (Brook 1985; ISRM 2007) ' $k_1 = 0.45$ ' when all rock samples were included.
 307 However, the resulting k_1 values for individual rock types were different to that suggested by
 308 ISRM (Brook 1985; ISRM 2007).

309

310 *Applicability of Existing Size Effect Models to Tensile Strength Results*

311 The tensile strength results from Gosford sandstone were used to assess which size effect
 312 model provides the best fit to the experimental data. For statistical model, a modified version
 313 of Eq. (7) similar to that suggested by Brook (1985) for point load strength index is proposed:

$$314 \quad \frac{\sigma_t}{\sigma_{t50}} = \left(\frac{50}{d} \right)^{k_2} \quad (13)$$

315 where, σ_t is the tensile strength, σ_{t50} is the characteristic tensile strength obtained from a
 316 sample with the characteristic size of 50 mm, d is sample size and k_2 has a same role as that
 317 for k_1 in Eq. (8) which controls the statistical decay of the strength with increase in size.
 318 Summary of the results of models calibration is presented in Table 10. Also, Fig. 22
 319 compares the resulting model predictions by different size effect models against the
 320 experimental data, followed by the relative error estimation of the prediction models. From
 321 Fig. 22 as well as Table 10 it is clear that SEL provided the best fit to the tensile strength data
 322 while statistical model resulted in poorest prediction and MFSL lies in between. This is an

323 ideal example to highlight the benefit of using a model with double constants over the one
324 with single constant. SEL and MFSL have two constants for model prediction while
325 statistical model relies only on one constant which is the strength of characteristic size (in
326 here 50 mm). Thus, the whole statistical model prediction shifted upward leading to the least
327 best fit compared to SEL and MFSL.

328

329 **Conclusion**

330 A suite of point-load and indirect tensile (Brazilian) tests were conducted on six different
331 rock types having various geological origins over a range of sizes. It was demonstrated that
332 all rock types follow the generalized size effect trend where an increase in size leads to
333 decrease in strength. Also, it was noted that in Brazilian test, an increase in size causes the
334 failure of intact rock transfers from pure tensile failure to a combination of shear and tensile
335 failure.

336

337 The applicability of three well-known size effect models based on statistics, fracture energy
338 and multifractals to point load and tensile strength data was investigated. It was confirmed
339 that, in addition to statistical size effect model, the fracture energy and multifractal size effect
340 models can suitably predict the size effect behaviour of point load results. Also, it was
341 demonstrated that the fracture energy size effect model provided the best fit to the tensile
342 strength data while the model prediction based on the statistical concept provided to the least
343 best fit.

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504

Table 1

Mean axial point load strength indices and the number of repetitions at different sizes for Bentheim sandstone

Sample diameter (mm)	Number of tests	Average of point load index, I_s (MPa)	SD	CV
			MPa	%
19	9	2.4	0.2	8.3
25	10	1.9	0.2	10.5
38	7	1.8	0.1	5.6
50	5	1.6	0.1	6.3
65	4	1.4	0.1	7.1

Table 2

Mean axial point load strength indices and the number of repetitions at different sizes for Gambier limestone

Sample diameter (mm)	Number of tests	Average of point load index, I_s (MPa)	SD	CV
			MPa	%
19	6	1.2	0.1	8.3
25	5	1	0.2	20
38	5	0.9	0.1	11.1
50	5	0.8	0.1	12.5
65	6	0.7	0.1	14.3

Table 3

Mean axial point load strength indices and the number of repetitions at different sizes for Granite A

Sample diameter (mm)	Number of tests	Average of point load index, I_s (MPa)	SD	CV
			MPa	%
19	6	18.2	3.4	18.7
25	4	17.3	2.2	12.7
38	6	14.4	0.9	6.3
50	5	10.7	1	9.3

Table 4

Mean axial point load strength indices and the number of repetitions at different sizes for Granite B

Sample diameter (mm)	Number of tests	Average of point load index, I_s (MPa)	SD	CV
			MPa	%
19	11	16.3	1.9	11.7
25	5	15.8	1	6.3
38	8	12.6	1.2	9.5
50	7	10.5	0.6	5.7
65	6	8.8	1.9	21.6
96	2	7.1	0	0

Table 5

Mean axial point load strength indices and the number of repetitions at different sizes for marble

Sample diameter (mm)	Number of tests	Average of point load index, I_s (MPa)	SD	CV
			MPa	%
19	5	2.9	0.6	20.7
25	9	2.7	0.4	14.8
38	8	1.7	0.3	17.6
50	9	1.7	0.4	23.5
65	8	1.6	0.4	25
96	3	1.5	0.1	5.3

Table 6

Mean tensile strengths for the different sizes of Gosford sandstone samples

Sample diameter (mm)	Number of tests	Average of tensile strength (MPa)	SD	CV
			MPa	%
19	5	3.4	0.42	12.4
25	5	3.3	0.8	24.2
38	5	3.2	0.3	9.4
50	5	3.2	0.3	9.4
65	5	2.8	0.4	14.3
96	5	2.5	0.2	8
118	5	2.4	0.3	12.5
145	5	3.4	0.1	2.9

Table 7

List of the fitting constants for statistical model, SEL and MFSL obtained from mean point load strength indices of sedimentary rocks

Sample	Statistical model, Eq. (8)		SEL			MFSL		
	k_1	R^2	Bf_t (MPa)	λd_0 (mm)	R^2	f_c (MPa)	l (mm)	R^2
Bentheim sandstone	0.38	0.92	4.3	7.61	0.92	0.82	133.23	0.93
Gambier limestone	0.39	0.97	2.31	6.57	0.97	0.38	161.15	0.98
Gosford sandstone	0.31	0.82	6.85	10.51	0.95	1.25	195.37	0.92

Table 8

List of the fitting constants for statistical model, SEL and MFSL obtained from mean point load strength indices of crystalline rocks

Sample	Statistical model, Eq. (8)		SEL			MFSL		
	k_1	R^2	Bf_i (MPa)	λd_0 (mm)	R^2	f_c (MPa)	l (mm)	R^2
Granite A	0.6	0.85	64.32	1.77	0.91	1.23	4475.42	0.91
Granite B	0.51	0.97	114.31	0.43	0.97	0.37	39724.53	0.97
Marble	0.54	0.88	36.58	0.12	0.89	0.49	632.15	0.9

Table 9

List of the fitting constants for statistical model, modified SEL and modified MFSL obtained from mean point load strength indices of all rock samples

Sample	Statistical model, Eq. (8)		Modified SEL		Modified MFSL	
	k_1	R^2	λd_0 (mm)	R^2	l (mm)	R^2
All rock samples	0.46	0.84	3.08	0.84	400.1	0.84

Table 10

List of the fitting constants for statistical model, SEL and MFSL obtained from mean tensile strengths of Gosford sandstone

Sample	Statistical model, Eq. (13)		SEL			MFSL		
	k_2	R^2	Bf_i (MPa)	λd_0 (mm)	R^2	f_c (MPa)	l (mm)	R^2
Gosford sandstone	0.16	0.41	3.85	77.5	0.94	2.36	24.59	0.77

Fig. 1. Cross-sectional areas of a) Bentheim sandstone, b) Gambier limestone, c) Gosford sandstone, d) Granite A, e) Granite B and f) Marble with 50 mm diameters

Fig. 2. Axial point load strength indices at different sizes obtained from Bentheim sandstone

Fig. 3. Axial point load strength indices at different sizes obtained from Gambier limestone

Fig. 4. Typical fracture patterns from axial PLT on Bentheim sandstone having 19, 25, 38, 50 and 65 mm diameters

Fig. 5. Typical fracture patterns from axial PLT on Gambier limestone having 19, 25, 38, 50 and 65 mm diameters

Fig. 6. Axial point load strength indices at different sizes obtained from Granite A

Fig. 7. Axial point load strength indices at different sizes obtained from Granite B

Fig. 8. Typical fracture patterns from axial PLT on Granite A having 25, 38 and 50 mm diameters

Fig. 9. Typical fracture patterns from axial PLT on Granite B having 38, 50, 65 and 96 mm diameters

Fig. 10. Axial point load strength indices at different sizes obtained from marble

Fig. 11. Typical fracture patterns from axial PLT on the marble at 25, 38, 50, 65 and 96 mm diameters

Fig. 12. Tensile strength data at different sizes obtained from Gosford sandstone

Fig. 13. Comparing the resulting fracture patterns of Gosford sandstone samples with various diameters after Brazilian tests

Fig. 14. The resulting fracture pattern from Brazilian test on graphite sample with 50 mm diameter reported by Serati (2015). The UCS of this sample was measured at about 100 MPa.

a)

b)

Fig. 15. a) Comparing three size effect models using the mean axial point load results from Bentheim sandstone and b) the resulting RE from three size effect models fitted to the mean point load strength indices of Bentheim sandstone at various sizes.

a)

b)

Fig. 16. a) Comparing three size effect models using the mean axial point load results from Gambier limestone and b) the resulting RE from three size effect models fitted to the mean point load strength indices of Gambier limestone at various sizes.

a)

b)

Fig. 17. a) Comparing three size effect models using the mean axial point load results from Gosford sandstone reported by Masoumi et al. (2016d) and b) the resulting RE from three size effect models fitted to the mean point load strength indices of Gosford sandstone at various sizes.

a)

b)

Fig. 18. a) Comparing three size effect models using the mean axial point load results from Granite A and b) the resulting RE from three size effect models fitted to the mean point load strength indices of Granite A at various sizes.

a)

b)

Fig. 19. a) Comparing three size effect models using the mean axial point load results from Granite B and b) the resulting RE from three size effect models fitted to the mean point load strength indices of Granite B at various sizes.

a)

b)

Fig. 20. a) Comparing three size effect models using the mean axial point load results from Marble and b) the resulting RE from three size effect models fitted to the mean point load strength indices of Marble at various sizes.

Fig. 21. Comparing three size effect models using the mean axial point load results from all rock samples

a)

b)

Fig. 22. a) Comparing three size effect models using the mean tensile strength results from Gosford sandstone and b) the resulting RE from three size effect models fitted to the mean tensile strength data of Gosford sandstone at various sizes.